

India \$ 5 Trillion Economy: Opportunities & Challenges

Dr. Sonali P Kumre

Assistant Professor, Faculty Department of Commerce, R.A. Arts, Shri M.K. Commerce
& Shri S.R. Rathi college, Washim – Maharashtra, India

Corresponding author- **Dr. Sonali P Kumre**

Email-sonalikumre2803@gmail.com

Abstract

India is one of the fastest growing economies in the world currently with a GDP of \$3.18 trillion at the end of financial year 2021. Indian economy has been on a fast growth since 2014 the economy was 1.7 trillion, from 2014 and over these years it has gradually become \$3.2 trillion economy this has inspired economy to become \$5 trillion economy by 2024 - 25 taking the earlier projections by International monetary fund India's GDP will touch dollar 4.7 trillion in 2024 but latest projection by IMF says India will reach \$ 5 trillion economy target by 2026 - 27 that is 2 years later than earlier projections achieve above set objective. India needs to grow at 9% per annum and increase its exports by \$1trillion. The current paper focuses on the drivers of economic growth followed by investment, productivity growth, job creation, demand and exports. The following paper is an attempt to address the issues of current economic slowdown and analyze strategies needed for India to become \$5 trillion economy in uncertain and disequilibrium world.

Key Words: GDP, PPP, Agricultural sector, Manufacturing sector, Service sector, IMF, World Bank

Introduction

India is one of the fastest growing economy in the world is currently rank as world's sixth largest economy with GDP of \$3.18 trillion in 2021 and continue to be world's third largest when GDP is compared on basis of purchasing power parity (PPP) at \$10.22 trillion in 21-22 Indian economy has been on growth path since 2014, India was \$1.7 trillion economy in 2014 in over 7 years 2021 its \$ 3.18 trillion economy almost having added up to \$1.48 trillion has inspired economy to become \$5 trillion economy by 2025. According to the World Bank data India lost out 5th spot to the UK in FY 22 by mere \$ 13 billion. The unprecedented Covid outbreak in early 2020 changed everything the government was forced to impose lockdown; on factories and other establishment so that Covid could be controlled after several rounds of relief measures announced by the government we are back to normal and economic activities gain some traction in March quarter final 2021. Now we are back on the path of achieving \$5 trillion, domestic policy makers have shifted the goal post of realizing \$5 trillion target by two years to 2027. so reaching the mark of \$5trillion will happen in this decade but question is when and how the *report of Commerce and industry minister* suggest that taking short and long term measures like the development of infrastructure, providing ease of living, and enhancing digital India, reducing paper work is of doing business and tackling

problem of pollution etc by 2024-25 India will become third largest economy in the world.

India: opportunities and initiative taken by Government of India

The GDP determine the country's economic health Gross domestic product refers to the total monetary value of the goods and services produce within one year. GDP constitutes a contribution done by all the three sectors of economy agriculture, Manufacturing and service sector. India requires annual growth rate of 9 percent in GDP to become \$5 trillion by 2025.

Let's take a look at the contribution of these sectors during pre and post Covid as follows:

Sector wise contribution in India's GDP

Agricultural Sector

It is estimated that India's agriculture sector accounts for around 14 percent of the country's economy but for 42 percent of total employment. The agriculture sector employed 145.6 million people in 2016-17. This increased by 4 per cent to reach 151.8 million in 2020-21. While it constituted 36 per cent of all employment in 2016-17, the figure rose to 40 per cent in 2020-21, underlining the sector's importance for the Indian economy. Employment in agriculture has been on the rise over the last two years with year-on-year (YoY) growth rates of 1.7 per cent in 2019-20 and 4.1 per cent in 2020-21. (*Business Standard Oct. 15 2022*)

GDP from Agriculture in India decreased to **4933.25** INR Billion in the second quarter of 2022 from **5688.80** INR Billion in the first quarter of 2022. *Source: Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MOSPI)* As per Provisional Estimates of Annual of National

Income, released by National Statistical Office (NSO), Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation on 31st May 2021, the share of Agriculture and Allied Sectors in Gross Value Added (GVA) of the country during the last three years at current prices is given below.

Year	Share of Agriculture and Allied sector to Total Economy (in percent)
2018-19	17.6
2019-20	18.4
2020-21	20.2

Source: National Statistical Office (NSO), M/o Statistics & PI. As per First Revised Estimates of National Income for 2019-20 released on 29th

January 2021, Gross Capital Formation (GCF) in agriculture and allied sectors at current prices during the last three years (latest available) is given below.

Year	Gross Capital Formation (GCF) of Agriculture, forestry and fishing at Current Price (₹ crore)
2017-18	3,62,706
2018-19	4,07,842
2019-20	4,46,044

Source: National Statistical Office (NSO), M/o Statistics & PI. India's agricultural sector has shown its resilience amid the adversities of COVID-19 induced lockdowns. The Agriculture and Allied activities clocked a growth of 3.4 per cent at constant prices during 2020-21 (first advance estimate) says the Economic Survey. The Union Minister for Finance & Corporate Affairs, Smt Nirmala Sitharaman presented the Economic Survey 2020-21 in Parliament.

Record Foodgrain Production

According to the Economic Survey in the Agriculture year 2019-20 (as per Fourth Advance Estimates), total food grain production in the country is estimated at record 296.65 million tonnes which is higher by 11.44 million tonnes than the production of food grain of 285.21 million tonnes achieved during 2018-19. Record food grains production of 316.06 million tonnes is estimated.

Union Minister for Agriculture and Farmers Welfare Shri Narender Singh Tomar

Agricultural Exports

The Economic Survey notes that in 2019-20, India's agricultural and allied exports amounted to approximately Rs. 252 thousand crores. The major export destinations were USA, Saudi Arabia, Iran, Nepal and Bangladesh. The top agriculture and related products exported from India were marine products, basmati rice, buffalo meat, spices, non-basmati rice, cotton raw, oil meals, sugar, castor oil and tea. While India occupies a leading position in global trade of aforementioned agri-products, its total agri-export basket accounts for a little over 2.5 per cent of world agri-trade.

Initiative taken by Government of India

1. Government has taken several steps for increasing investment in agriculture sector such as
2. Enhanced institutional credit to farmers;

promotion of scientific warehousing infrastructure for increasing shelf life of agricultural produce; setting up of Agri-tech Infrastructure Fund for making farming competitive and profitable;

3. Developing commercial organic farming etc. Government is implementing various schemes for supply of farm inputs, like seeds, fertilizers, agricultural machinery and equipments, irrigation facilities, institutional credit, etc., at subsidized rates to the farmers in the country.
4. Government has recently taken several steps for increasing investment and growth in agriculture sector which include creation of Long Term Irrigation Fund (LTIF), Micro Irrigation Fund for water use efficiency, promotion of commercial organic farming, etc. The details of such major schemes /steps are given below.

Government of India has launched the Central Sector Scheme of financing facility under Agriculture Infrastructure Fund (AIF) to boost Agriculture Infrastructure relating to post harvest management and community farming assets. Under these scheme entities such as farmers, agri - entrepreneurs, starts up, Central/ State agency or local body sponsored public private partnership projects etc. can take benefit for setting up eligible infrastructure projects. Under Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) Scheme of Ministry of Agriculture, grants-in-aid are given to state governments on the basis of the projects approved in State Level Sanctioning Committee Meeting (SLSC). States can take up projects for the development of Agriculture and allied sector in Public Private Partnership (PPP) for Integrated Agriculture Component.

Further, Government of India has launched the Aatmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan (ABA) to strengthen Infrastructure, Logistics, Capacity Building, Governance and Administrative Reforms for Agriculture. **Union Minister of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare Shri Narendra Singh Tomar in Lok Sabha).**

Manufacturing & Service sectors

India's gross domestic product (GDP) at current prices stood at Rs. 51.23 lakh crore (US\$ 694.93 billion) in the first quarter of FY22, as per the provisional estimates of gross domestic product for the first quarter of 2021-22. The manufacturing GVA at current prices was estimated at US\$ 77.47 billion in the third quarter of FY22 and has contributed around 16.3% to the nominal GVA of during the past ten years. India has potential to become a global manufacturing hub and by 2030, it can add more than US\$ 500 billion annually to the global economy. India's display panel market is

estimated to grow from US\$ 7 billion in 2021 to US\$ 15 billion in 2025. As per the survey conducted by the Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry (FICCI), capacity utilisation in India's manufacturing sector stood at 72.0% in the second quarter of FY22, indicating significant recovery in the sector. Due to factors like power growth, long-term employment prospects, and skill routes for millions of people, India has a significant potential to engage in international markets. Several factors contribute to their potential, Digital transformation being a crucial component in achieving an advantage in this fiercely competitive industry, technology has today sparked creativity.

Manufacturing sector in India is gradually shifting to a more automated and process driven manufacturing which is expected to increase the efficiency and boost production of the manufacturing industry.

India is gradually progressing on the road to Industry 4.0 through the initiatives like the National Manufacturing Policy which aims to increase the share of manufacturing in GDP to 25 percent by 2025 and the PLI scheme for manufacturing which was launched in 2022 to develop the core manufacturing sector at par with global manufacturing standards.

The government's focus on manufacturing through program's such as 'Make in India' and policies such as the 'National Policy for Advanced Manufacturing', Industry 4.0 could play a key role in boosting the manufacturing sector's share in the country's GDP to 25% by 2022 from the current 17%, (**Mahendra Nath Pandey, Minister of Heavy Industries and Public Enterprises**).

The platform would allow investors to identify and apply for various pre-operation clearances needed for starting business in the country. "This will certainly ease the biggest challenges of multiple stakeholders' approval and the platform will do away with the need for multiple applications across various departments," the focus on manufacturing will help India in leveraging its demographic dividend, as the vast youth population of the country can be engaged in the sector. "This mandates a strong skilling focus to enhance employability and reduce the burden on the agricultural industry. However, India would need to strike a balance between emerging technologies and the country's massive labour force by investing in high technology sectors, as well as in the development of labour-intensive sectors," **Vineet Agarwal, president, ASSOCHAM**.

Apart from this India is an attractive hub for foreign investments in the manufacturing sector. Several mobile phone, luxury and automobile brands among others have setup or looking for establishing their bases in the country. **The Indian Cellular and**

Electronic Association (ICEA) forecasts that the economy has potential to enhance its cumulative laptop and tablet manufacturing capacity to US\$ 100billion by 2025 through policy interventions.

Issues related to manufacturing sector

1. The Make in India the government’s first flagship goal towards making India self-reliant aimed to increase the share of the manufacturing sector to 25 per cent of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Other plans like Startup India and other policies aimed at boosting the manufacturing capabilities of the nation have also cooled off in recent years.
2. But experts suggest that the goal may not be realized by 2025 or even by 2030 due to the lack of infrastructure development in pipeline.
3. The Centre for Economic Data & Analysis and Centre For Monitoring India Economy said in that manufacturing employment is nearly half of what it was 5 years ago
4. Manufacturing accounts for nearly 17 per cent of India’s GDP but the sector has seen employment decline sharply in the last 5 years. From employing 51 million Indians in 2016-17, employment in the sector declined by 46 per cent to reach 27.3 million in 2020-21. All sub-sectors within manufacturing registered a longer-term decline.
5. Employment in manufacturing, real estate & construction, and mining sectors. Together these sectors accounted for 30 per cent of all employment in 2016-17, which came down to 21 per cent in 2020-21.
6. These numbers show that the employment crisis in India predates the pandemic; the Covid-19 pandemic has made the jobs plight even more severe.

Service Sector

The services sector is the largest sector of India. Gross Value Added (GVA) at current prices for the services sector is estimated at 96.54 lakh crore INR in 2020-21. The services sector accounts for 53.89% of total India's GVA of 179.15 lakh crore Indian rupees. The Economic Survey highlighted that India had a dominant presence in global services exports. It remained among the top ten services exporter countries in 2020, with its share in world commercial services exports increasing to 4.1% in 2020 from 3.4% in 2019. “The impact of Covid-19 induced global lockdown on India’s services exports was less severe as compared to merchandise exports”, stated the *Economic Survey*. The Survey further mentioned that despite Covid-19 impact on transport exports, double digit growth in gross exports of services, aided by exports of software, business and transportation services, resulted in an increase of 22.8% in net exports of services in H1 2021-22.

The services, sector is not only the dominant sector in India’s GDP, but has also attracted significant foreign investment, has contributed significantly to export and has provided large-scale employment. India’s services sector covers a wide variety of activities such as trade, hotel and restaurants, transport, storage and communication, financing, insurance, real estate, business services, community, social and personal services, and services associated with construction.

The Economic Survey noted that the Services Sector was the largest recipient of FDI inflows in India. During H1 2021-22, Services Sector received \$ 16.73 billion FDI equity inflows. “*Financial, Business, Outsourcing, R&D, Courier, Tech testing & Analysis along with Education sub sector witnessed strong FDI inflows*”, mentioned the Survey.

The services sector of India remains the engine of growth for India’s economy and contributed 53% to India’s Gross Value Added at current prices in

FY21-22 (as per advance estimates). India’s services sector GVA increased at a CAGR of 11.43% to Rs. 101.47 trillion (US\$ 1,439.48 billion) in FY20, from

Rs. 68.81 trillion (US\$ 1,005.30 billion) in FY16. Between FY16 and FY20, financial, real estate and professional services augmented at a CAGR of 11.68% (in Rs. terms), while trade, hotels, transport, communication and services related to broadcasting rose at a CAGR of 10.98% (in Rs. terms). India's IT and business services market is projected to reach US\$ 19.93 billion by 2025.

Challenges before Indian Economy

1. The agriculture sector employed 145.6 million people in 2016-17. This increased by 4 per cent to reach 151.8 million in 2020-21. While it constituted 36 per cent of all employment in 2016-17, the figure rose to 40 per cent in 2020-21, underlining the sector's importance for the Indian economy. Employment in agriculture has been on the rise over the last two years with year-on-year (YoY) growth rates of 1.7 per cent in 2019-20 and 4.1 per cent in 2020-21.
2. Manufacturing accounts for nearly 17 per cent of India's GDP but the sector has seen employment decline sharply in the last 5 years. From employing 51 million Indians in 2016-17, employment in the sector declined by 46 per cent to reach 27.3 million in 2020-21. This indicates the severity of the employment crisis in India predating the pandemic.
3. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) last month slashed its global growth projections for 2022 and 2023, and warned of a possible worldwide recession next year. IMF's forecasts came at a time when the US economy had already shrunk by 1.5% in the March quarter and many fear that growth may have slipped into the negative zone in the June quarter as well. Chances are that the US Federal Reserve rate hikes to check runaway inflation will cause a deeper recession in the world's largest economy by the end of the year or early next year.
4. "We expect GDP to grow by 14%-14.5% year-on-year in Q1 FY23 backed by low base and strong domestic demand," (*Ritika Chhabra, Economist and Quant Analyst, Prabhudas Lilladher*). "A broad based pickup was observed across consumption, services industry and investment. We expect the private final consumption expenditure – a measure of demand, and gross fixed capital formation – a measure of investment, to grow by 16% and 14%, respectively. However, net exports will be a drag due to high average crude price during Q1," Chhabra added.

Conclusion:

India continues to be one of the fastest-growing economies in the world, and its macro fundamentals have improved dramatically in recent years. Although we look at a relatively favorable growth

rate, that is supported by only a small part of the economy, that doesn't mean into significant growth of income for all the households. The near \$600 billion in forex reserves gives policy-makers the confidence that the country can easily cope with any external headwind. With a focus on Aatmanirbhar Bharat initiative and the creation of an investor-friendly eco-system, things are improving. So, even if the goal post has to be shifted, it may not go too far and India is going to be a \$5-trillion economy during the 2020s only, still few points' needs to address here like:

Productivity per unit labour time is highest in the services sector, but the challenge is to enhance labour-value addition from services, and reduce employment-dependency on agriculture and to boost manufacturing sector.

The Production-Linked Incentive Scheme introduced by the government is incentivizing corporate investment, but rising import bills for fossil energy are increasing the trade deficit and breaking down the import coverage capacity of foreign exchange reserves," the report observed. UNCTAD

In Indian economy only 20 per cent of the women are participating in the labor market. "That is a problem that has to be addressed, just by extending social security system, is not enough, important is that people should be given the tools to generate income themselves," *Hans Trimmer Chief economist south Asia*.

What seen in the region and to some extent in India also is that the government was not really prepared to absorb all those shocks that we are seeing in the region, The COVID shock, the war in Ukraine and the commodity prices are once in a lifetime shocks and they come one after the other and then the environmental disasters also," *Hans Trimmer Chief economist south Asia*.

Initiative of government's land acquisition Bill, makes sense to allocate land to potential investors in suitable industrial clusters where they don't have to bother about obtaining various onerous approvals, including environmental ones. Efforts must be stepped up to engage with states to implement the four labour codes on wages, social security, industrial relations and occupation safety, health and working conditions, which the Centre has proposed.

Another important requirement will be to firm up a viable policy to promote the public-private partnership (PPP) in the country. Not all the business can be setup by government; this is the only way out for infrastructural development. The PPP model hasn't quite worked in India (apart from the limited success in the road sector). The government has proposed to come out with a new PPP policy. Let's see how it works.

With all the above suggestions by economists and initiative being taken by government of India, Indian Economy will definitely soon cross \$5 trillion mark.

Web References

1. <https://www.ibef.org/industry/manufacturing-sector-india>
2. <https://www.livemint.com/economy/manufacturing-would-contribute-25-of-gdp-by-end-of-2022-11629897419400.html>
3. <https://www.indiatoday.in/business/story/explained-why-india-s-economy-needs-a-manufacturing-push-1846038-2021-08-27>
4. <https://www.business-standard.com/article/economy-policy/ceda-cmie-bulletin-manufacturing-employment-halves-in-five-years->
5. <https://www.outlookindia.com/website/story/business-news-gdp-data-the-story-of-indias-manufacturing-sector/393296>
6. <https://www.financialexpress.com/economy/gdp-q1fy23-double-digit-growth-likely-in-first-quarter-as-economy-fights-back-from-covid-to-full-recovery/2650123/>
7. <https://pib.gov.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=231150>
8. <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1741942>
9. [https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1693205#:~:text=India's%20agricultural%20sector%20has%20shown,estimate\)%20says%20the%20Economic%20Survey.](https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1693205#:~:text=India's%20agricultural%20sector%20has%20shown,estimate)%20says%20the%20Economic%20Survey.)
10. <https://tradingeconomics.com/india/gdp-from-agriculture>
11. <https://www.business-standard.com/article/economy-policy/ceda-cmie-bulletin-manufacturing-employment-halves-in-five-years->
12. <https://youtu.be/Oa0vBexdTjY>
13. <https://youtu.be/wSHKM40-4Ek>
14. <https://www.financialexpress.com>
15. <https://www.business-standard.com>
16. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications>
17. <https://www.dailyo.in/business/economy-gdp-growth-economic-slowdown-5-trillion-economy->
18. <https://www.fortuneindia.com/macro/india-to-grow-57-in-2022-slow-down>
19. <https://www.financialexpress.com/budget/economic-survey-2022-live-fm-nirmala-sitharaman-finance-ministry-india-economy-report-card-gdp-growth-projection>
20. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/economy/indicators/swaminathan-aiyar>
21. <https://www.newindianexpress.com/business/2022/may/22/usd-5-trillion-economy-the-curious-case-of-indias-rise-to-the-top-5-2456444.html>